

Rental And Loan System In Agriculture Using Blockchain Technology

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ABSTRACT

Over the last several years, blockchain technology has garnered a lot of interest. The development of on-chain smart contracts, which allow for the operation of decentralized apps in trust-free settings, has contributed to this new pattern. Attacks that take advantage of flaws in smart contracts are rising in tandem with their use. Several methods, including the documentation of vulnerabilities and the use of formal verification for model checking, have been studied to mitigate these assaults and prevent breaches. However, the characteristics of the block-chain and user behavior are lost in these methods. The smart agricultural industry is rapidly growing into a world-changing financial powerhouse. Major forces propelling this technical, ecological, and economic movement include the need for greater food quality and the ability to monitor weather and soil conditions in real time. The potential for smart contract technologies to be integrated into smart agriculture to improve not only the quality of agricultural outputs but also the efficiency of the associated supply chain and agricultural logistics is investigated in this work.

Keywords: Rental, Loan, Block-Chain, Agriculture.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 About Blockchain

In 2008, a person (or group of persons) going by the name Satoshi Nakamoto came up with the idea for the first blockchain. Nakamoto introduced a difficulty parameter to regulate the pace at which blocks are added to the chain and a Hashcash-like technique to timestamp blocks without having them to be signed by a trusted entity, both of which were significant improvements to the architecture. The next year, Nakamoto implemented the idea as the public ledger for all Bitcoin network transactions, making it a central component of the cryptocurrency.

The numerous nodes that make up a blockchain all share the same copy of the ledger. The entries in this ledger are immutable and replicated on all nodes. These nodes may be placed anywhere is most convenient. A series of blocks form this ledger. The Genesis Block is the first block in the chain, and it is unique in that it does not include any transactions or the hash of the preceding block. The first ever blockchain transaction is included in the second block, which also serves as a reference to the genesis block. This method is shown in the figure. As can be observed, the Prev.Hash field in the genesis block is blank. The first block indicates the genesis block, while the second indicates that the first block will be reached very soon.

Fig-1: Architecture of a Blockchain

Blockchains are decentralized and open ledgers that may be accessed by anybody on the network. Information recorded in a blockchain cannot be easily modified once it has been recorded.

Blockchain is a distributed ledger of records that can not be changed without a lot of work and is encrypted so that only authorized parties may access it. Each block includes transaction data, a timestamp, and a cryptographic hash of the prior block. A digital signature is used to verify the legitimacy of each transaction on a blockchain. The blockchain is immutable because of the encryption and digital signatures used to secure the data. Display of Results This algorithm is used to verify trades and add new blocks to the Blockchain. Consensus refers to the process through which all members in a network agree on a shared set of terms. A blockchain is a digital ledger in which all transactions are recorded and shared among all users. In this method, there is no need for a third party to prevent fraud or duplicate transactions.

To better grasp blockchain, think of a scenario in which you are seeking for a way to transfer money to a buddy who lives in a distant part of the world. A bank account or a mobile money transfer service like PayPal or Paytm are two common options. Because this option requires the use of intermediaries to complete the transfer, a processing charge will be withheld from your funds. The safety of your funds is also compromised in this scenario, since a hacker may easily interrupt the network and take them. The client loses out in both scenarios. Blockchain technology can help with this.

If we utilize a blockchain to transfer funds instead of a bank, the procedure is streamlined and safe. When you handle the payments yourself, you avoid paying a processing charge to a middleman. All the data and records stored on the blockchain are open and distributed over the network, since the blockchain database is distributed and not confined to a single place. There is no way for a hacker to compromise the data as it is not kept centrally.

1.2 PROBLEM DEFINITION

The main issue with current studies is that farmers are losing money owing to a lack of resources (such as machinery, labor, and land). Every year, many farmers leave the profession because of these difficulties. Farmers would benefit greatly from the adoption of this suggested system, which will allow them to continue farming in the most efficient and cost-effective manner possible.

1.3 OBJECTIVES

- To create smart contracts on the Ethereum network, a high-level language has been developed.
- To design a consistent and immutable data structure of blockchain nodes in order to propose a system architecture for a blockchain-based distributed agriculture traceability system.
- In this research, we created a blockchain-based certificate system and a distributed application.
- This technology was chosen due to its invulnerability, encryption, traceability, and ability to synchronize data. The system is more efficient overall since blockchain characteristics have been integrated into it.
- Truffle, a blockchain infrastructure construction platform.

1.4 PROPOSED SYSTEM

To ensure confidentiality and get agreement, a blockchain network uses public and private keys to generate a digital signature. After these keys have been used to ensure authentication, the requirement for authorisation will emerge. Through mathematical verification and agreement amongst network members, blockchain makes it possible to settle on any arbitrary value with absolute certainty. The sender uses their private key to authenticate the transfer and broadcasts the details of the transaction to the network. Digital signatures, timestamps, and the recipient's public key are only some of the data that is stored in a block. This data chunk is then sent out onto the network, where verification may begin. In order to complete the transaction, miners all across the network begin working on the corresponding mathematical problem. The miners will have to put in some serious CPU time to crack this problem. In exchange for being the first to solve the riddle, miners are rewarded with bitcoins. Mathematical issues of this

kind are known as proof-of-work problems. A block is added to the blockchain after the majority of nodes in the network have reached agreement and agreed on a common solution and a time stamp has been generated. Anything from currency to data to communications may be stored in this block. When a new block is added to a blockchain, all of the nodes in the network immediately get updated versions of the blockchain.

1.5 LIMITATIONS

1. Lack of Standardization: Lack of uniformity is a problem when using smart contract technology to smart agriculture. It is difficult to design interoperable and scalable solutions across many agricultural systems since different smart contract platforms may use different programming languages, frameworks, and features.
2. Adoption Challenges: Smart contracts need to be widely adopted by farmers, agricultural businesses, and other stakeholders in order to be implemented in the agricultural sector. There may be reluctance or opposition to embracing new technologies owing to issues such a lack of technical experience, high implementation costs, and worries about data privacy and security.
3. Limited Scalability: Scalability is a major issue for smart contracts built on the blockchain as the number of users and transactions grows. Smart contracts in large-scale agricultural operations may be hampered by the transaction speed and throughput constraints of existing blockchain networks.
4. Data Accuracy and Reliability: Accurate and trustworthy data, such as current weather and soil conditions, is crucial to smart agriculture. Smart contracts rely on information gathered from sensors and other IoT devices; nevertheless, this information is not immune to inaccuracy, prejudice, or manipulation. For smart agricultural initiatives to be successful, it is essential that data be reliable and accurate.
5. Regulatory and Legal Challenges: There may be legal and regulatory hurdles to overcome if smart contract technology is widely used in the agricultural sector. Contract legality, responsibility, dispute resolution, and conformity with current agricultural rules may be ambiguous and complicated depending on the country. In order to overcome these difficulties, we need well-defined legal frameworks and regulations.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

[1] Author Xiong F. et. Al (2019) Describes the added time, money, and information waste inherent in conventional construction supply chains as a result of information intermediaries. Therefore, we offer a proposal for a Blockchain-based construction supply chain to loosen up regulations in some sectors. The proposed blockchain-based solution for the construction industry's supply chain would use a distributed ledger to keep tabs on and coordinate everything from raw materials to finished products. Using blockchain technology may cut down on the number of middlemen involved in a transaction. Smart contracts, which are programmed to be carried out when specific criteria are satisfied, might be feasible in a blockchain-based model of the construction supply chain.

[2] The Author Fu Y & Zhu J (2019) In this research, the author proposes a dual storage structure of "database + blockchain" that integrates on-chain and off-chain traceable information in order to lower the load strain of the blockchain and enhance the efficiency of information inquiry. That is, only a subset of the data is kept on the blockchain itself; the remainder is kept in a more conventional database. Safe and secure transmission of sensitive data inside the blockchain network is guaranteed by the use of cryptography in conjunction with the blockchain technology. To protect the privacy and authenticity of transmitted information, cryptography makes use of encoding and decoding. Cryptography is employed in the context of blockchain to guarantee that only valid users may see and make changes to the ledger.

[3] The author Chandra Sekhar Bhusal (2021) describes how this research, by evaluating current literature and case studies of blockchain start-up enterprises, investigates the possible use of blockchain technology in the agricultural sector and seeks to solve existing challenges. The authors contend that blockchain technology offers a potentially useful strategy for developing a future agri-foods system that is safer, better, more sustainable, and more reliable. Food safety, traceability, and supply chain transparency are just some of the problems that the agricultural sector may employ blockchain technology to solve. Farmers, processors, distributors, and retailers may use

blockchain technology to verify the provenance, quality, and safety of agricultural goods along the supply chain, from the farm to the table, by means of a distributed ledger system. This may help guarantee that people are receiving nutritious, environmentally friendly foods.

[4]The author Natalia A. Popova, Natalia G. Butakova (2019) This essay explores the safeguards built into distributed databases and suggests utilizing blockchain technology without tokens to address the issue of data duplication. It also suggests ways in which blockchain technology might be integrated into today's financial infrastructures. Due to their superior data availability, fault tolerance, and scalability, distributed databases are quickly gaining in popularity. Due to the ease with which data may be duplicated and updated across several nodes, ensuring that data in these databases remains unique is a substantial difficulty.

[5]The author Hiten Patel (2019) The suggested AgriOnBlock architecture may be used as a guide for creating a Rental and Loan System that bridges the gaps between the agricultural industry's many players. A blockchain-based platform may be used to construct the Rental and Loan System, making it possible for tenants, lenders, and farmers to conduct safe, transparent transactions. To ensure accountability and the smooth execution of transactions, the system may leverage smart contracts to automate the rental and loan process, much as AgriOnBlock. The Rental and Loan System may have many levels, including an API, an app, and a blockchain. The user interface layer may facilitate simple system interaction for farmers, lenders, and tenants. Different modules, including as loan management, rental management, and payment processing, can make it possible for parties to interact with one another without any hitches at the application layer.

3. SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

All computer programs need the presence of additional hardware components or other software resources before they can be utilized to their full potential. These are often seen more as suggestions than hard and fast rules and are known as (computer) system requirements. The majority of programs specify dual sets of hardware and software needs.

3.1 Hardware Requirements

In the case of operating systems, a hardware requirements list is often accompanied by a hardware compatibility list (HCL), which details which components of the system are supported by the OS or application. In the parts that follow, we will talk more specifically about the gear you will need.

Processor	- 2.5 GHz or above
RAM	- 4GB or above
Hard Disk	- 256 GB or above
Internet Connection	

3.2 Software Requirements

A software requirements specification (SRS) is a document that details the features and functionality that must be built into a program. It may also include a list of use cases that illustrate how the product's end users will interact with it. It also includes necessary but optional features. Design or implementation limitations are a result of non-functional needs.

Operating System - Windows 8 or above/Ubuntu 10 or above
Technology - Blockchain
Programming Tools:

- Ganache-client or Ganache
- Node JS, MySQL
- HTML5, CSS, Bootstrap.
- Solidity 0.4.5

4. DESIGN OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

The next step, after the requirement selection, is design. There are primarily four different layouts in this section.

1. Architectural Design
2. User interaction and use case Design

Fig-2: Architecture of blockchain network with respect to algorithm

A blockchain is a distributed ledger consisting of a series of blocks. Despite its earlier discovery, Blockchain technology was not widely used until Satoshi Nakamoto created Bitcoin in 2009. Bitcoin, the first digital money, was established by him using Blockchain technology. Let us get down to brass tacks and learn how a blockchain operates.

A blockchain network consists of blocks, each of which contains data and a hash of the prior block. A hash is the unchanging mathematical fingerprint of a given block. The block's hash will change in the event of any changes to the contents of the block. What makes blockchain safe is the way blocks are linked together using their own unique hash keys.

Every time a transaction is made on a blockchain, it must be verified by one of the network's nodes. These nodes are known as miners on the Bitcoin blockchain, and they use proof-of-work to process and verify network transactions. Each block must have a reference to the hash of the prior block for the transaction to be considered legitimate. Only if the hash checks out will the exchange take place. If a hacker compromises the network and alters data in a single block, that block's associated hash will also be altered.

The breach will be discovered once the compromised hash is incompatible with the original hash. By making it simple to see any effort to tamper with the chain of blocks, this ensures the blockchain's immutability.

A blockchain is a distributed ledger that stores data or information in blocks rather than a single repository. The first working version of the previously discovered blockchain technology was developed in 2009 by an anonymous

individual or group using the moniker Satoshi Nakamoto. Bitcoin was the first decentralized digital currency, and it relied on the blockchain ledger to function.

Let us take a deeper look at how a blockchain really functions:

1. **Block Structure:** Blocks are the building blocks of a blockchain. Each block in a blockchain contains transactions or data that is important to that application. In the Bitcoin network, for instance, a block is a group of confirmed transactions. In addition, the data in each block is used to build a cryptographic code called a hash, which serves as a unique identification. The hash may be thought of as the block's unique digital fingerprint.

2. **Hashing:** A hash function is a mathematical technique that, given an arbitrary amount of input data, returns a string of characters of a predetermined length. In a blockchain, the hash of the prior block is included in each new block. By connecting them by their hashes, blocks form a chain in which any changes to the contents in a single block render all future blocks useless. This feature protects the immutability and security of the blockchain.

3. **Immutability and Tamper-Resistance:** A blockchain's immutability is the result of its connected structure and cryptographic hashing. It becomes increasingly difficult to alter the data inside a block once it has been added to the chain without being recognized. If data in a block were to be changed, the hash of that block and all blocks after it would need to be recalculated. Because of this, altering the blockchain becomes prohibitively costly computationally and impractical in a decentralized network.

4. **Network Consensus:** Transactions or blocks in a blockchain network are validated and verified by various nodes. Miners are the nodes that participate in validating Bitcoin transactions. Proof-of-work is a challenging mathematical challenge that miners strive to solve. When a miner finds a solution to an issue, they will often broadcast it to the network so that other nodes may verify and accept it. To keep the blockchain consistent and secure, its members use a consensus process to verify that newly added transactions are accepted by the network as a whole.

5. **Security and Attack Resistance:** Because of its distributed structure and consensus process, blockchains are inherently secure and resistant to malicious assaults. The hashes of all following blocks would need to be recalculated if, for instance, a hacker attempted to edit a transaction inside a block. However, since the blockchain is decentralized across many nodes, the vast majority of users would reject the altered version, protecting the integrity of the original data and foiling any potential attacks.

Blockchain technology guarantees the safekeeping, verification, and recording of any kind of information by using cryptographic hashing, decentralized consensus procedures, and the immutability of connected blocks. Numerous sectors are investigating its potential for increasing openness, efficacy, and confidence in a wide range of processes and systems outside the realm of cryptocurrencies.

USECASE DAIGRAM FOR MACHINERY POOL

Fig-3: Machinery Pool

USECASE DAIGRAM FOR BANKING TRANSACTIONS

Fig-4: Banking Transactions

5. MODULES DEVELOPED

The four levels of the aforementioned architecture are the "Application" or "front end" layer, the "contract" layer, the "blockchain virtual network" layer, and the "transaction" layer.

Fig-5: Architecture with respect to application

Application layer:

Smart contracts make up the application layer. The application layer has two sub-layers that are the application layer and the execution layer, respectively. Users engage with the blockchain network using apps found at the application layer. It is made up of several components such as scripts, APIs, UIs, and frameworks. These apps often link to the blockchain network using application programming interfaces (APIs). Smart contracts, underlying rules, and chaincode are all part of the Execution Layer. The executable code and regulations are located in this sublayer. The semantic layer (the smart contracts and rules) is responsible for the validation and execution of a transaction before it is passed on to the application layer and the execution layer. To execute transactions and guarantee the deterministic character of the blockchain (in the case of permissioned blockchains like Hyperledger fabric), applications transmit instructions to the execution layer (chaincode).

Contract layer:

Each contract in it is designed to carry out a certain function. Implacability of smart contracts. Solidity is the programming language used to create Ethereum smart contracts. A compiler is required for syntactical proof of the code. Because of the compilation process, the bytecode is compact and executes quickly on EVM. Any code running on EVM is completely separated from the rest of the computer and has no access to the disk or network.

Smart contract: The EVM stores and references the business logic code at a specific location. The actions specified in a smart contract are carried out when a corresponding transaction is processed. A smart contract's state may be updated in response to a transaction depending on the contract's underlying logic. Smart contracts may be written in any programming language, from Solidity to Python, and then compiled into bytecode using a dedicated compiler. Once a smart contract has been deployed, it is given a specific URL. Using the blockchain, anybody may carry out a transaction in accordance with that smart contract. For an overview of how a transaction works on the Ethereum blockchain, see below. In order to execute, smart contracts are written in a high-level language like Solidity and then deployed to EVM. However, the smart contract is connected to the real world by other codes, such as those for inter-blockchain communication and logic execution. We refer to them as "dApps" or "oracles."

Transaction layer:

The transaction layer acts as a repository for all the data generated by the application layer and the contract layer's transactions, making that data accessible to all the other levels. Transactions: A blockchain's transactions are what give it value. They are the fundamental units of a blockchain network. There are three main parts to each given transaction: the recipient's address, the sender's address, and the amount. In many ways, this is similar to any other purchase seen on a credit card account.

A Bitcoin transaction is the sending of bitcoin from one Bitcoin address to another. When a transaction occurs, the consensus-verified blockchain is updated. A blockchain is a distributed, decentralized, and public ledger. This implies that each node (user of the blockchain system) has its own copy of the blockchain and that the current known "state" is determined by applying a hash function to each transaction in the blockchain in the order in which it occurs. Each node receives a block containing a collection of transactions. Each node in the network checks and "processes" new transactions as they are broadcast across the system. The data on a blockchain is the flow of currency, which is checked and processed in various ways depending on the implementation.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig-6: Farmer pool bank

Fig-7: Loan recovery details

Fig-8: Utilities provided for agriculture

Fig-9: Details of Equipments

Fig-10: Loan purpose and payment details

Fig-11: Metamask with demo eth account

Fig-12: Loan recovery code

```

24 <div class="row">
25 <div class="col">
26 <div class="card">
27 <div class="card-header">
28 <h3>Harvesting</h3>
29 <p>State: <a class="btn btn-primary" style=" color: white;padding: 0px 5px;font-size: 0.8rem;
30 >">Interest Returns</a></p>
31 </div>
32 <div class="card-body">
33 <div class="card-text">
34 <p><b>Address: </b>0azf645dasf46ds64f6s4ad6fs6d4f6ds<br>
35 <b>Borrower: </b>0azf645dasf46ds64f6s4ad6fs6d4f6ds<br>
36 <b>Requested: </b>10 ETH<br>
37 <b>Funded: </b>12 ETH</p>
38 <b>Installments Count: </b>2<br>
39 <b>Interest: </b>2 ETH<br>
40 </div>
41 </div>
42 <div class="card-footer text-muted">
43 <a href="#" class="btn btn-primary">Get Interest</a>
44 <a href="#" class="btn btn-warning">Revoke Vote</a>
45 <a href="#" class="btn btn-warning">Refund</a>
46 <a href="#" class="btn btn-danger">Fraud</a>
47 </div>
48 </div>
49 </div>
50 <div class="col">
51 </div>
52 </div>
53 </div>
54 </div>
55 </div>
56 </div>
57 </body>
58 </html>

```

Fig-13: Loan recovery code

```

2 <html lang="en">
3 <head>
4 <meta charset="UTF-8">
5 <meta http-equiv="X-UA-Compatible" content="IE=edge">
6 <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1.0">
7 <title>Farmer Utility Pooling</title>
8 <link rel="stylesheet" href="assets/css/style.css">
9 <link rel="stylesheet" href="assets/css/bootstrap.css">
10 <style>
11 <body {
12 background-image: url("assets/img/hero-bg.png") !important;
13 }
14 </style>
15 </head>
16 <body>
17 <div class="container">
18 <div class="text-center p-5">
19 
20 <div class="head p-2 pool-title">
21 <h1>Farmer Pool Bank</h1>
22 </div>
23 </div>
24 <div class="p-5 mt-3">
25 <div class="text-center pool-dec">
26 <p>Lorem ipsum dolor, sit amet consectetur adipiscing elit. Odio, sit labore! Vel accusantium omnis ipsum beatae placeat explicabo modi animi incidunt ea
27 <div class="row text-center">
28 <div class="col pool-box m-5">
29 <div><h3>Contribute</h3></div>
30 </div>
31 <div class="col pool-box m-5">
32 <div><h3>Take-Loan</h3></div>
33 </div>
34 </div>
35 </div>
36 </div>
37 </div>

```

Fig-14: Pool bank code

```

1 <!DOCTYPE html>
2 <html lang="en">
3 <head>
4 <meta charset="UTF-8">
5 <meta http-equiv="X-UA-Compatible" content="IE=edge">
6 <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1.0">
7 <title>Farmer Utility Pooling</title>
8 <link rel="stylesheet" href="assets/css/style.css">
9 <link rel="stylesheet" href="assets/css/bootstrap.css">
10 </head>
11 <body>
12 <style>
13   body {
14     background-image: url("assets/img/hero-bg.png") !important;
15   }
16 </style>
17 <div class="container">
18 <div class="text-center">
19 <div class="head p-2 pool-title">
20 <h1>Take Loan</h1>
21 </div>
22 </div>
23 <div class="p-5 m-5">
24 <div class="text-center pool-dec mb-5">
25 <p>Lorem ipsum dolor, sit amet consectetur adipisicing elit. Odio, sit labore! Vel accusantium omnis ipsum beatae placeat explicabo modi animi incidunt ea
26 </p>
27 </div>
28 <form>
29 <div class="form-group">
30 <label for="agr-purpose">Agriculture Purpose:</label>
31 <input type="text" class="form-control" id="agr-purpose" aria-describedby="agr-purpose" placeholder="Enter Purpose">
32 </div>
33 <div class="row">
34 <div class="col">
35 <div class="form-group">
36 <label for="req-amt">Requested Amount:</label>
37 <input type="number" class="form-control" id="req-amt" aria-describedby="req-amt" placeholder="Minimum 2ETH">

```

Fig-15: Code for take loan

```

Administrator: Command Prompt - ganache-cli
eth_getBlockByNumber
net_version
eth_getBlockByNumber
eth_estimateGas
eth_blockNumber
net_version
eth_blockNumber
eth_getBlockByNumber
eth_sendTransaction

Transaction: 0x1104ad287025343e4596dcba09c4938489af1c1655305c65c2efd419c11410c0
Contract created: 0xba22593a154e1bcad38091e25e4d68d6e376c47d
Gas usage: 232207
Block Number: 1
Block Time: Sat May 23 2020 16:21:59 GMT+0530 (India Standard Time)

eth_getTransactionReceipt
eth_getCode
eth_getTransactionByHash
eth_getBlockByNumber
eth_getBalance
eth_getBlockByNumber
eth_getBlockByNumber
eth_sendTransaction

Transaction: 0x87770be8f4522bab62e8cd6f4dbf0559b5ba9874111894cb0cdfa12876df7a0
Gas usage: 43221
Block Number: 2
Block Time: Sat May 23 2020 16:22:00 GMT+0530 (India Standard Time)

eth_getTransactionReceipt
eth_getBlockByNumber
eth_accounts
eth_blockNumber
net_version
eth_getBlockByNumber
eth_getBlockByNumber
net_version
eth_getBlockByNumber
eth_estimateGas
net_version
eth_blockNumber
eth_getBlockByNumber
eth_sendTransaction

Transaction: 0x5e0808086d76c1a08130d53705616530dc0d332d1016d4d4890ff6d436c4
Contract created: 0xa5e76b0b0293c96abb029ec400a20212c44f3e1
Gas usage: 64845
Block Number: 3
Block Time: Sat May 23 2020 16:22:00 GMT+0530 (India Standard Time)

```

Fig-16: Ganache-cli creates virtual blockchain

7. CONCLUSION

Many thousands of tons of grain are purchased annually from growers all throughout the nation. This project has provided a summary of how blockchain technology might be used to the purchasing process to improve efficiency. Finding out whether and how smart contracts are more efficient than the present system was another goal of this research. It is now up to the Indian government to determine whether and when blockchain technology will be implemented. Due to the possibility of unfinished business in this project, it is important to do a cost-benefit analysis to determine whether or not blockchain technology is the best solution. This work also demonstrates how blockchain can be used to lessen the prevalence of fraud and scam against unsuspecting farmers, keep records safe and secure so they can not be lost, obtain precise daily transaction details, quickly retrieve records, guarantee that farmers receive the promised goods and services, and improve food safety and security. The project also exemplifies the reduction of power held by the intermediary (the guy at the procurement center) and the subsequent automation of the process. It may be possible in the future to expand this application nationwide, so that all of the states and territories participate in a single blockchain at the national level. Instead of creating a whole blockchain from scratch, it is possible to study the implementation of Hyper Ledger and Ethereum.

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